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Research Article

**OUTCOMES AND SURVIVAL RATE AFTER
CARDIOPULMONARY RESUSCITATION; A DESCRIPTIVE
ANALYSIS****¹Dr Muhammad Awais Ebrahim, ²Dr Yousaf Aziz, ³Dr Muhammad Asif Shahzad**¹Frontier Medical College, Abbottabad²Shalamar Medical and Dental College, Lahore³Islamic International Medical College, Rawalpindi**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) has been known in its current form since 1960. Different studies have shown results ranging from different countries. Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess CPR and survival in the treatment of heart attacks patients.

Place and Duration: In the emergency department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from January 2019 to December 2019.

Work plan: This cross-sectional examination was conducted in the Emergency department of Mayo Hospital Lahore, all patients admitted to the emergency department with a heart attack were enrolled. We use a pre-designed registration form and hospital documentation to retrieve the attached patient data. The main results are the rate of success of CPR and the survival rate of these patients.

Results: Of the 855 patients, 510 (59.64%), were men Patients. A total of 101 (11.82%) patients have been discharged from the hospital. Various factors, such as cardiac arrest and previous health problems, have affected the likelihood of success in CPR and the survival of cardiac arrest patients.

Conclusion: The survival rate of patients discharged from the hospital was less than a third of the patients, and about half of the patients were successful in CPR. More intensive care facilities and training interventions for emergency personnel and communities can improve the survival of patients who have had a heart attack in our healthcare system.

Keywords: Resuscitation, Cardiac Arrest, Survival, Application, Ambulance.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cardiac arrest is a fatal phenomenon in adults due to various arrhythmias, such as active-screen pulsez (VT), impulse electrical activity (PEAs), ventricular fibrillation or the heart system. Although the use of closed chest CPR (CPR) first described in the 1960s has expanded widely, post-cardiac arrest survival is generally poor. Recently, several CPR response essay studies have focused on identifying factors that affect patients' chances. Some compared different survival rates in different time zones of the day and on different days of the week, short- and long-term prognosis after CPR in the hospital, type of survival or detention after witness and unsent arrest, depending on the age of the patients. On the other hand, different studies in this area have shown that accurate resuscitation rates based on different factors are not the same between different centres. This data can be used to improve maintenance delivery processes and improve the level of training of hospital staff to make appropriate equipment decisions, including a better training programme. Different survival rates at hospital discharge have been reported in different studies conducted in different countries. The aim of this study was to assess the success rate of CPR and survival in the treatment of cardiac arrest in patients at a training medical center.

METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was carried out in the emergency department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from January 2019 to December 2019. All patients who were taken to the emergency room due to arrest or hospital detention and eventually performed CPR were included. Patients who were taken to the emergency room and were almost worried did not receive CPR, patients who had a heart attack, and patients who had respiratory tracts were omitted from the study without a heart attack.

A pre-designed data registration form was used to collect patient information. Including questions about CPR, recent patient condition, duration of CPR, heart rate of patients prior to arrest, patients' previous medical problems and whether a witness was arrested. Age, gender, smoking, drug use and alcohol consumption, cardio-ac retention and cause were also investigated. Hospital documents at the emergency room were used to gather information for each patient. The CPR score was considered effective only if the patient had spontaneous respiration and detectable heart rate. To ensure their final condition, patients were observed until the end of their hospital stay.

All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 18.0. The identification of statistical analysis was carried out for all demographic characteristics, patient variables and results. Fisher's final study and Chi-square test were used to compare the differences between groups of patients with successful or unsuccessful CPR and patients who survived until discharged from the hospital or whose hospital stay had expired. The survival rate was calculated as dividing the number of survivors into the total CPR population after discharge from hospital.

RESULTS:

Of the 855 patients, 510 (59.64%), were males. The CPR process was successful among 364 (42.58%) and the remaining 491 (57.42%) considered unsuccessful. A total of 101 (11.82%) patients were discharged from the hospital without neurological sensitivity and neurological deficit (discharged from the hospital). Among patients who had extreme vitality after discharge from hospital, 81 patients (22.25%) without neurological deficits and 20 (5.5%) have been neurologically written out. Other 263 (72.25%) patients expired before discharge from the hospital, even though they had successful CPR.

The mean age of patients receiving successful CPR ranged from 60.5 to 11.4 years, while in patients receiving failed CPR, the age was 65.11-13.7 years. The patients discharged from the hospital are over 63 years old, 68 years (18.99%) under 63 years of age (P=0.016).

A total of 225 (44.11%) (P=0.063) compared to male patients 139 (40.28%). The number of women discharged alive was 40 (11.59%).

CPR time: The average CPR process time was among patients considered to have successful CPR of 16.06 minutes (SD 0.999) and 43.48 minutes (15.75 for SD) was among others who received a failed CPR process. Among patients discharged from the hospital was statistically lower than in patients who fell before discharge from the hospital (on average 12.8 minutes, SD 6.8, P to 0.040)

The analysis of the data showed that the rate of success of CPR in cardiac arrest in the hospital in case of cardiac arrest was statistically higher (P = 0.047 and up to 0.012).

Witness heart attack: Some heart attack incidents have been witnessed by family, emergency personnel or strangers, others have not. Different CPR outputs are associated with the entity and witness type, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Different CPR outcomes regarding witnessed or unwitnessed cardiac arrest

	Total frequency (%)	Successful CPR (%)	Unsuccessful CPR (%)
Family	154 (18.01)	61 (39.61)	93 (60.39)
Staff of emergency ward	641 (74.97)	291 (45.39)	350 (54.61)
Strangers	37 (4.32)	6 (16.21)	31 (83.79)
No witness	23 (2.69)	5 (21.73)	18 (28.27)

Previous health problems: Patients in the past have had various previous health problems, and the success rate of CPR differs from their correlation, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Different Medical problems among patients and different CPR outcome in each one

	Total frequency (%)	Successful CPR (%)	Unsuccessful CPR (%)
Hypertension	235 (28.17)	93 (39.57)	142 (60.43)
History of MI	67 (8.03)	20 (29.5)	47 (70.5)
History of IHD	311 (37.29)	141 (45.67)	170 (45.33)
Pacemaker	12 (1.43)	6 (50)	6 (50)
History of valvular heart disease	9 (1.08)	2 (29.22)	7 (70.78)
History of DM	137 (16.42)	41 (29.92)	96 (83.48)
History of CVA	88 (10.5)	67 (76.14)	21 (23.86)
	35 (4.19)	25 (71.42)	10 (28.58)
Asthma and/or COPD	72 (8.63)	39 (54.16)	33 (45.84)
History of Liver disease	10 (1.02)	2 (20)	8 (80)
Cancer	31 (3.71)	7 (22.58)	24 (77.42)
AIDS	3 (0.35)	0 (0.0)	100%

Different cardiac rhythms were detected prior to receiving CPR including asystole (720 patients, 84.21%), VF (48 patients, 5.6%), VT (39 patients, 4.43%), PEA (29 patients, 3.47%) and bradycardia (18 patients, 2.15%). Rates of successful CPR was 308 (42.77%), 31 (67.39%), 28 (75.63%), 19 (65.51%) and 11 (61.11%) respectively. The Chi-square analysis showed no statistically significant correlation between the previous heart rate and CPR or hospital survival rate (P=0.10 and P=0.14, respectively)

Patients' habits in relation to CPR outcome: Our sample included 139 patients (16.66%) who were cigarette smokers, among those 49 (35.25%) received successful CPR. Another 71 patients (8.51%) were addicted and 28 (39.43%) of them received successful CPR. Within the included patients, 9 (1.08%) had drunk alcohol recently, among those 3 (33.33%) received successful CPR.

DISCUSSION:

In our study, about half of patients received successful CPR, and after discharge from the hospital, the survival rate was less than a third.

In addition, our study found that factors such as those under the age of 63, cardiac arrest at the emergency room and CPR of less than 12.8 minutes are associated with a higher survival rate in discharge from hospital. The only factor associated with a higher rate of successful CPR was cardiac arrest, which took place at the emergency room. CPR had no effect on CPR or survival before discharge to hospital, neither gender nor cardiopulmonary rhythm.

Compared to other international studies, studies conducted in the United States from 1992 to 2005 showed that during this period, survival rates in American hospitals were 18.3%. Similarly, an explanatory study conducted in Spain between

2003 and 2006 showed that survival was 20% after discharge from hospital. Another retrospective survey of 383 companies in Pakistan between 1998 and 2003 showed that survival was 19% after being discharged from hospital. In addition, another study conducted in a developing country between 2003 and 2006 showed that only 7.4% of patients experienced high levels. Compared to this study, a previous pro-spective study of 206 patients in Keşan, Iran, reported a survival rate of 5.3% discharged from the hospital in 2002. Compared to all of these searches, our study seems to have an acceptable survival rate among developing countries. Although it is lower than in developed countries, the survival rate in Iran has increased over the last 6 years.

Effects for apps

Despite a successful CPR procedure in about half of patients, only 11.82% of patients can be

discharged from the hospital. Given that the majority of patients who receive a successful CPR procedure should be admitted to intensive care, this finding can be attributed to inadequate intensive care or insufficient participation in other healthcare in our hospital. In other words, it can be said that the resuscitation process in our country should be more detailed and further initiatives are needed to improve it. This development should focus both on the opening of hospital facilities and on increasing the crisis training process. Facilities such as more intensive care beds and the development of private shock management rooms in hospitals can be very effective in managing patients after CPR. In addition, various factors, including emergency information, can affect survival, improving training programs will lead to better management of these conditions not only for hospital staff but also for the community.

CONCLUSION:

Less than a third of patients discharged from the hospital, and about half of the patients underwent successful CPR. Emergency personnel and more intensive care and community training interventions can improve survival rates for patients who have had a heart attack in our healthcare system.

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